

GraspOS SCOPE+i Resource:

Guide on the diversity of OS contributions, roles and activities

Full resource

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Introduction to the guide

Summary

This guide discusses the wide range of open science (OS) contributions and activities that need to be recognized when evaluating and assessing research. OS affects and is affected by many stakeholders like researchers themselves, individuals consuming research like practitioners and the general public. They all should work together to address social and cultural barriers and challenges of OS. This guide is useful for both evaluators and researchers.

Explore also Open science assessment guide <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15525630>. The guide highlights OS outputs, activities and contributions that are relevant to consider in all types of research assessment processes.

Guide as part of SCOPE+i Resources and in relation to SCOPE Framework

The [SCOPE+i Resources](#) aim to facilitate the transition towards Responsible Research Assessment (RRA) with particular focus on contributions to OS. Being one out of 17 resources (guides, templates and checklists), this guide supports the structured organization of research assessment process and information from initial planning through to the publication of assessment protocols.

[SCOPE framework](#) is a five-stage model for evaluating responsibly. It is a practical step-by-step process designed to help research managers, or anyone involved in conducting research evaluations, in planning new evaluations as well as checking existing evaluations. SCOPE is an acronym, where S stands for START with what you value, C for CONTEXT considerations, O for OPTIONS for evaluating, P for PROBE deeply, and E for EVALUATE your evaluation. This guide is most relevant for the stages O and P.

Figure 1. SCOPE Framework by INORMS (2023) (modified by highlighting the most relevant stages for this resource).

More about SCOPE Framework in International Network of Research Management Societies (INORMS) - Research Evaluation Group (2023). The SCOPE Framework. The University of Melbourne. Report. <https://doi.org/10.26188/21919527.v1>

All SCOPE+i Resources are brought together in the [GraspOS Infrastructure](#) (i), a simple, user-friendly interface (UI) where you can explore project results and save documents to learn and share with others.

Values and principles of open science

The [UNESCO Recommendation on Open Science](#) (2023) has defined OS as follows:

“Open science is a set of principles and practices that aim to make scientific research from all fields accessible to everyone for the benefit of scientists and society as a whole. Open science is about making sure not only that scientific knowledge is accessible but also that the production of that knowledge itself is inclusive, equitable and sustainable.”

For the UNESCO member states this means that

- the states are recommended to engage actively in removing the barriers for OS
- assessment of scientific contribution and career progression is rewarding good OS practices
- there is a need to change the current research culture to recognize researchers for sharing, collaborating and engaging with other researchers and society
- research assessment and career evaluation systems should be reviewed in order to align them with the principles of OS

Values of OS:

- quality and integrity
- collective benefit
- equity and fairness
- diversity and inclusiveness (UNESCO, 2023)

Principles of OS

- transparency, scrutiny, critique and reproducibility
- equality of opportunities
- responsibility, respect and accountability
- collaboration, participation and inclusion
- flexibility
- sustainability (UNESCO, 2023)

Organisations that are members of the [Coalition for Advancing Research Assessment \(CoARA\)](#) or signatories of [The Agreement on Reforming Research Assessment](#) (ARRA) are committed to reform their research assessment practices and processes. This means, among other things, recognizing the diversity of research outputs and activities and an emphasis on qualitative judgment, which can be supported by a responsible use of quantitative methods. Openness and transparency of research and research processes are key pillars to be considered in ARRA.

Open science contributions, roles and activities

Stakeholders and contributors in scientific research

Stakeholders are individuals or groups who affect or are affected by OS. They include those who produce knowledge (researchers, research teams, organizations), those who use, apply, or regulate it (practitioners, the public, policymakers, funders, government bodies, regulatory agencies), and those who form part of the scholarly ecosystem (journals, repositories, archives, data stewards, librarians, technologists, infrastructure experts, standards organizations, CRIS vendors, institutional leaders, and open scholarship trainers) (Almarzouq et al., 2023; Jones & Murphy, 2021).

Research contributors are defined broadly as anyone involved in the administration, design, conduct, or dissemination of research, beyond the traditional definition of “researcher.” This includes engineers and support staff whose contributions are vital but often remain invisible without recognition in authorship or contributor lists (Jones & Murphy, 2021).

Researchers play a central role in implementing OS. Whenever confidentiality does not prevent it, research projects should be made publicly accessible to ensure broad dissemination. Achieving this requires adequate technical infrastructure, training, recognition, and incentives, which together enable OS and OS-aligned RRA practices. In addition, the policies of research funders and publishers regarding the openness of publications and data are critical for promoting OS and shaping researchers’ activities.

The Contributor Role Taxonomy, CRediT

In the spirit of OS, credit should be acknowledged to whom it belongs. The Contributor Role Taxonomy, [CRediT](#), can be used to describe the key types of contributions typically made to the production and publication of research output such as research articles. In 2022 CRediT was approved as an [ANSI/NIOS standard](#).

CRediT taxonomy defines 14 contributor roles:

1. Conceptualization – Ideas; formulation or evolution of overarching research goals and aims.
2. Data curation – Management activities to annotate (produce metadata), scrub data and maintain research data (including software code, where it is necessary for interpreting the data itself) for initial use and later re-use.
3. Formal analysis – Application of statistical, mathematical, computational, or other formal techniques to analyze or synthesize study data.
4. Funding acquisition - Acquisition of the financial support for the project leading to this publication.
5. Investigation – Conducting a research and investigation process, specifically performing the experiments, or data/evidence collection.
6. Methodology – Development or design of methodology; creation of models.

7. Project administration – Management and coordination responsibility for the research activity planning and execution.
8. Resources – Provision of study materials, reagents, materials, patients, laboratory samples, animals, instrumentation, computing resources, or other analysis tools.
9. Software – Programming, software development; designing computer programs; implementation of the computer code and supporting algorithms; testing of existing code components.
10. Supervision – Oversight and leadership responsibility for the research activity planning and execution, including mentorship external to the core team.
11. Validation – Verification, whether as a part of the activity or separate, of the overall replication/reproducibility of results/experiments and other research outputs.
12. Visualization – Preparation, creation and/or presentation of the published work, specifically visualization/data presentation.
13. Writing – original draft – Preparation, creation and/or presentation of the published work, specifically writing the initial draft (including substantive translation).
14. Writing – review & editing – Preparation, creation and/or presentation of the published work by those from the original research group, specifically critical review, commentary or revision – including pre- or post-publication stages.

So far, CRediT taxonomy is available in thirteen languages

<https://contributorshipcollaboration.github.io/projects/translation/completed/>.

Complex scholarly communications ecosystem

The scholarly communications ecosystem is a complex, multi-stakeholder environment with strong network effects. The situation can be complicated by conflicting ambitions of, and competitions between, stakeholders across all levels of the open scholarship framework. (Jones & Murphy, 2021). Still, a variety of stakeholders should work together to address social and cultural barriers and challenges of OS.

Gabrier Bammer highlights in Embo Reports (2021) different levels of stakeholder engagement. Mutual informing, consultation, involving, collaborating and empowering between researchers and all relevant stakeholders is needed.

Opening science to society and having dialogue with indigenous people, marginalized scholars and local communities via (open) science policies, complies with the values of OS. (UNESCO report, 2023). Cole et al. (2024) have studied societal impact of OS. Their findings show that OS generates societal impact in terms of education and awareness, climate and environment, engagement, policy and governance, equity and empowerment, health, and trust and attitudes toward research. Findings also show that the evidence is presented primarily attributed to the impact of citizen science (CS).

OS encourages collaboration across academia, industry, public authorities, and citizen groups. When all groups participate in the research and innovation process, creativity and trust in science can potentially increase. This engagement process leads to greater transparency in the research process, greater potential impact of research, more efficient research processes and opportunities for global scientific collaboration.

Diversity of OS skills

OS activities and skills can be presented in various ways. Below are some examples.

The European Union has identified eight pillars of OS presented e.g. on the [University College of London \(UCL\) page](#). The pillars are FAIR data, research integrity, next generation metrics, future scholarly communication, citizen science, education and skill, rewards and initiatives, and [EOSC, European Open Science Cloud](#). Read more about EOSC in the chapter [Systems and tools](#) in this document.

In 2019, [Digital Skills for Library Staff and Researchers Working Group](#) embarked on a project to define the skills needed for OS, and to align them with [LIBER's 2018-2022 Strategy](#). The visualisation of OS skills ([McCaffrey et al. 2020](#)) serves as a structured guide to help individuals and institutions identify the specific skills they need to learn or teach in order to embrace Open Science practices.

[European Commission \(2017\)](#) groups OS skills into four larger categories:

1. Skills and expertise necessary for open access publishing.
2. Skills and expertise regarding research data, data production, management, analysis/use/reuse, dissemination and a change of paradigm from “protected data by default” to “open data by default”, respecting legal, and other constraints.
3. Skills and expertise to act in and beyond one’s own scholarly and disciplinary community.
4. Skills and expertise resulting from a general and broad concept of citizen science, where researchers interact with the general public to enhance the impact of science and research.

All of these skills are needed at different levels by the research system, whether by researchers or technicians as well as support and administrative staff, depending on the role that these various functions have in an Open Science research environment (European Commission, 2017).

Examples of systems and tools

Besides stakeholders OS requires e.g. integrations of systems and shared taxonomies like [CRedit](#) which is to be integrated with both [ORCID](#) and [Crossref](#).

[European Open Science Cloud](#) (EOSC) provides researchers a federated and open multi-disciplinary environment where researchers can publish, find and reuse data, tools and services for research, innovation and educational purposes. It links existing interoperable infrastructures to enable even greater collaboration between researchers and research domains. EOSC services can be browsed via [EOSC Hub](#). All scientific resource providers in Europe are invited to contribute research objects - such as data, software, services, and tools – in the EOSC EU Node to support the mission of promoting Open Science.

Interoperability of systems facilitates and reduces the researcher's work. Openly available tools (databases, infrastructures) for searching and discovering information, designing study, collecting and analyzing data and finally publishing and reporting help to make research open and transparent.

[OpenEdition](#) is a platform dedicated to electronic resources in the humanities and social sciences. As part of OpenEdition, [Hypotheses](#) is a digital platform designed for researchers in the Social

Sciences and Humanities (SSH) to interact with scholars and engage with society through academic blogging. Hypotheses is free and open to the public.

HAL is a multidisciplinary open archive for the sharing of published and unpublished research. It is at the service of researchers in academic institutions, both public and private. In France, HAL is the national archive chosen by the scientific and academic community for the open dissemination of its research results. The repository is also at the service of researchers affiliated to foreign academic institutions, whether public or private.

Episciences is a diamond OA scientific publishing platform covering all disciplines. It offers an innovative tool, integrated into the European ecosystem for the distribution of content, and an editorial support. Episciences has received funding from the European Union's under grant agreement OpenAIRE Nexus - OpenAIRE-Nexus Scholarly Communication Services for EOSC users (101017452).

Make Data Count is an initiative that promotes the development of open data metrics to enable evaluation of data usage. Make Data count is supported by DataCite and Wellcome Trust.

Jisc Open policy finder (formerly Sherpa services) helps authors and institutions to make informed and confident decisions on OA publications and compliance. Open policies can be searched by journal, publisher or funder.

Narrative CV is a flexible and adaptable tool for different disciplines and career stages. It can be used to highlight how a researcher has communicated ideas and research results, both written and verbally. OS can be integrated inside modules or - if preferred - OS can be an additional module.

Explore Guide on promoting OS contributions in a narrative CV

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